

Stability of Unsaturated Compounds in Presence of Catalysts.

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The instability of acetylene, ethylene, propylene and trimethylethylene in presence of nickel or copper at 200° has been exhaustively shown by Sabatier and Senderens (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1899, 21, 530; *Compt. rend.*, 1900, 130, 250; 1902, 134, 1127); they found that under these conditions acetylene spontaneously decomposed with the deposition of carbon and with the formation of various aromatic liquid products and cuprene $n(C_7H_8)_2$. In some experiments on catalysis, a mixture of naphthalene vapour and acetylene was passed over nickel at 200° but surprisingly there was no decomposition; similar results were obtained with naphthalene and ethylene; benzene with acetylene or ethylene behaved in an identical way. This stability of acetylene and ethylene was evidently due primarily to dilution with benzene or naphthalene. When however phenylethylene (styrolene) was passed over nickel and not the slightest decomposition was observed even at 350°, it became apparent that the stability of the unsaturated linkages might be also due to the influence of contiguous groups. The present work is an attempt to investigate this question. Besides Sabatier and Senderens' work, other researches have been done on the decomposition of acetylene and ethylene and other unsaturated compounds. Thus Moissan and Moureau (*Compt. rend.*, 1896, 122, 1241) have observed that finely divided platinum decomposes acetylene at 150° spontaneously and there is so much evolution of heat that the metal becomes incandescent. Mailhe in a series of papers has shown the course of decomposition of oleic acid, oleins and other unsaturated glycerides when they are passed over reduced nickel (*Compt. rend.*, 1922, 174., 873; *Ann. Chim.*, 1922, 17, 304). But so far no attempt has been made, in such catalytic decompositions, to find out the influence of the contiguous groups, attached to the unsaturated linkages. The stabilising influence of phenyl radicle, as was observed in the case of phenylethylene, was also seen when phenylacetylene was treated in a similar way and

found to remain undecomposed. Eugenol was only partly transformed into *isoeugenol*. Sym.-diphenylethylene was found to be quite stable. Ethyl cinnamate in which the group $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$ is attached to phenyl and carbethoxy radicles did not suffer any decomposition but the case was otherwise with cinnamic acid, alcohol and aldehyde.

Cinnamic acid decomposed in two ways, normally like formic and acetic acids (Sabatier and Mailhe, *Compt. rend.*, 1911, 152, 1212).

and abnormally with the production of benzene, phenylacetylene and diphenylethylene probably according to the following equations:—

Nearly 90% of the cinnamic acid decomposed and the products consisted of 70% phenylethylene, 10% benzene, 10% phenylacetylene and 10% diphenylethylene. $\frac{2}{3}$ Phenylacetylene did not seem to have been formed from phenylethylene as the latter under the conditions of the experiment was found to be stable. Cinnamic alcohol and aldehyde at 350° decomposed into phenylethylene.

These results show that the carbethoxy group like phenyl has stabilising influence on the unsaturated linkage whereas the groups. CO_2H , CHO , CH_2OH cannot protect it.

Experiments with coumarin gave coumarone presumably according to the following equation:—

Ethyl acetoacetate (enolic) decomposed into acetone, carbon dioxide and ethylene. Here it may be noted that although of the two stabilising groups, *viz.*, phenyl and carbethoxy, the latter is present, there is another hydroxyl group which makes the whole system labile and thus hastens the decomposition.

The reaction products were detected and identified. The results so far obtained may be summarised thus:—

(a). Phenyl and carbethoxy groups have stabilising influence on unsaturated linkages.

(b). The groups CH_2OH , CO_2H and CHO cannot protect the unsaturated bonds. Further experiments in this line are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reduced Nickel.—Commercial nickel nitrate was converted into the oxalate; this was heated on the sand-bath when nickel oxide was obtained in a very porous form. It was then reduced at 300° in a current of purified hydrogen.

Experiments with Cinnamic Acid.

Vapours of cinnamic acid were passed over the catalyst at 350° and a product was obtained which on fractionation gave—

Fraction (a), b. p. $80-82^\circ$, which was identified as benzene.

Fraction (b), b. p. $135-142^\circ$. It was found to be phenylacetylene as it gave the characteristic reaction with silver nitrate (white ppt.) and with copper sulphate (yellow ppt.); when treated with sulphuric acid it gave acetophenone which was identified.

Fraction (c), b. p. $146-150^\circ$. It was identified to be phenylethylene; it gave a dibromo-derivative, m.p. 74° ; the m.p. was not depressed by admixture with a genuine specimen of styrolene dibromide.

Residue.—It was repeatedly washed with hot water and sodium carbonate solution to eliminate cinnamic acid and was then crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 124° ; the picrate melted at 237° . (Found: C, 93.58; H, 6.44. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}$ requires C, 93.33; H, 6.66 per cent.).

Hence the substance was diphenylethylene.

Coumarin.—Vapours of coumarin were passed over nickel at 350° and the liquid obtained on fractionation gave primarily a product boiling at 100°, the bromo-derivative of which melted at 88°. These facts point out that the liquid is coumarone.

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